

Carbon Credits as a 'Bundle of Rights': Applying Rawlsian Justice for the Benefit-sharing and Carbon Rights Protection of the Least-advantaged (Indigenous) in the Republic of Congo

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Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation (REDD+) has emerged as a cornerstone of global forest conservation and management policy. It operates as a performance-based mechanism that incentivises forest conservation and restoration to lower atmospheric carbon levels. The Republic of Congo is a deforestation front characterised by low deforestation rates and has engaged in collaborations with international organisations, other nations, and local communities to adapt its national frameworks, integrating carbon rights and redistributing REDD+ benefits. The contractual framework presupposes the involvement and recognition of the rights of indigenous communities in the management of their 23.9 million hectares of forest carbon stocks. This aligns with REDD+ under the FCCC Paris Rulebook, which emphasises safeguards for indigenous rights protected by the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP) and promotes benefit-sharing through Emission Reduction (ER) Programs. However, the fragmented nature of policy initiatives and projects targeting deforestation raises concerns about how the rights of vulnerable communities are protected. Using a Rawlsian perspective, the paper assesses whether the country's benefit-sharing mechanisms effectively support the protection and enhancement of carbon rights associated with local and indigenous forests, taking into account community expectations and compensation for these rights. The discussion shifts from simple monetary payments to entitlement to revenue, arguing that payments for carbon rights should consider the overall REDD+ governance and advocate for reforms in land tenure laws to enable individuals, families, and communities to claim land and tree rights, addressing issues of fairness in REDD+ and Payments for Environmental Services (PES) schemes.

Keywords: REDD+, redistribution, benefits, rights, local communities, republic of Congo

REDD+ actions in a specific country directly impact the rights of local and indigenous communities who rely on the forest or hold operating permits for agricultural and industrial activities (Alemagi et al., 2014). Within a theoretical framework focused on a bundle of rights, actions undertaken under REDD+ that limit the exercise of statutory or customary rights must compensate for the loss of profits (loss of win) based on both legal and equity principles. The sharing of costs related to these actions and the compensation for the losses incurred should therefore be at the heart of the national debate on REDD+, as well as the attribution of new rights related to reducing greenhouse gas emissions and sequestering carbon to generate the necessary funds.

Traditionally, carbon rights are viewed as a component of an owner's land rights (Cotula & Mayers, 2009). That means the rights to carbon would necessarily belong to the person who owns a legal land title. The entity holding the right to the forest land is usually considered the owner of the primary emission rights (Kengoum et

al., 2024). These rights derive from the right over the land and the right to use the forest. However, a conundrum arises when the government controls land and forests, raising concerns about the rights of indigenous populations to carbon credits. In this context, indigenous populations' rights over the carbon credits, even when they live on the land, raise a great deal of concern. Such concerns cannot be raised when local communities or indigenous people hold a right to use the forest, whether this right is customary or codified, they also likely hold forest carbon rights. This is also obvious in the context of private land. The primary right of ownership over the carbon forest from private lands and forests belongs to the owner thereof. This approach, however, is said to be simplistic, as it relies on the concept of land ownership. A different approach would consider carbon rights as a form of property, rather than a form of real estate. In the latter, it becomes transferable at any time, and not only during its creation. Carbon credits can be allocated or transferred to individuals or communities who have no land ownership rights, but it is necessary to establish the legal means by which such a transfer is possible and to recognise this right to them.

Despite the potential of REDD+ carbon financing, one cannot benefit from the money financing the purchase of carbon rights, unless the person owns the carbon credit or benefits from the corresponding "carbon rights" (Calel, 2011). Thus, benefits can only be realised if carbon rights are clearly codified. The latter is new and is therefore not yet defined in the national laws of many countries likely to sell their carbon rights. In the Republic of Congo, REDD+ is implemented in conjunction with national laws governing the expansion of the forestry, agricultural, agro-industrial, mining, and tourism sectors. Nevertheless, the existing regulatory framework

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fails to provide adequate protection for the rights of vulnerable rural communities, particularly Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities (IPLC). Consequently, customary lands may be allocated for REDD+ pilot projects without obtaining free, prior, and informed consent (FPIC) or ensuring just compensation. Addressing this land tenure insecurity is a critical legal predicament that requires urgent attention to ensure IPLC can genuinely benefit from REDD+ initiatives. This analysis examines the impact of this tenure insecurity and the resulting vulnerability of IPLC within the context of REDD+ in the Republic of Congo. Particularly, how should this notion be legally understood in the context of the Republic of Congo, and how can the local and indigenous people who own or use forests as their primary resource for survival benefit from carbon rights? To legally apprehend this in Congo, particularly for those relying on forests for survival, the paper scrutinises international environmental laws. Moving away from mechanisms under the Kyoto Protocol (UNFCCC/CP/2001/13/Add) which are largely irrelevant at present, this analysis focuses on obligations established under the Paris Agreement and current financial mechanisms that underpin the legal standards on intergenerational equity and climate change.

Whatever the case may be, carbon rights are likely to be defined within the context of a REDD+ mechanism, under the UNFCCC and the Kyoto Protocol, as well as those allocated by treaty to the various Parties. By adopting laws that incorporate international law into national law, a government may decide to transfer and regulate the ownership of carbon rights in the national context. These legal frameworks are the starting point for conceptualising the carbon rights of local and indigenous communities and benefit-sharing mechanisms.

Thus, the paper proceeds in two main parts. The first part describes the country's potential in terms of carbon emissions and assesses the potential benefits that may be generated through REDD+. If shared equitably with local communities, these benefits may compensate for the loss and promote the rights of indigenous and local communities. The second part examines the legal frameworks, both national and international, governing carbon rights. In particular, how the Congolese national legal framework provides for the carbon rights of local and indigenous communities who own forest and land rights, whether these rights are customary or legal, or have at least the right to use the forest for their survival. In doing so, the paper considers certain constitutional provisions and also relies on conventional treaties, which form part of the national law, as the country follows a monist system. Particularly, the paper relies on the post-Kyoto Protocol mechanisms established by the Paris Agreement, which constitute the basis for conferring carbon rights on parties in the form of assigned amount units (AAUs) and authorising the creation of credits through voluntary mechanisms. Due to the country's capacity to enhance the implementation of REDD+, the paper synthesises that the rights to carbon emissions are established both under international and national laws; however, the redistribution of such rights to benefit indigenous and local communities should form part of the country's national budget, supported by a control mechanism and rooted in strong political will.

Post-Kyoto and Recent Development in REDD+ Frameworks

Although the Kyoto Protocol initially established the groundwork for carbon mechanisms via the Clean Development Mechanism

(CDM) and Joint Implementation (JI), it is now the Paris Agreement frameworks that primarily oversee REDD+ implementation, focusing on nationally determined contributions (NDCs) and voluntary carbon markets (Schneider et al., 2024).

In essence, the international market mechanisms for reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and related regulatory systems have undergone different distinct periods, each with specific challenges (Nomani, 2020). These periods, spanning from 1997 to 2018, are marked by various events. From the operationalisation of the Kyoto Protocol mechanisms, specifically the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) and Joint Implementation (JI), to the expansion of the REDD+ market. The JI mechanism enables parties listed in Annex I to trade, transfer, or acquire carbon credits. Such an activity is subject to several conditions, including the quantifiable project capacity to reduce or limit emissions. Likewise, Decision 6/CP.7 of the Marrakech Accord, together with Article 6, provides the basis for a legal framework for the Joint Implementation Mechanism. Notably, parties interested in participating in the JI must develop national guidelines and procedures for approval projects. This is to allow the supervisory committee to verify any emissions-reduction project. Given the strictness of this mechanism, parties that are in full compliance with the eligibility requirements for participation in the Kyoto Protocol trading mechanisms are exempt from other internationally imposed requirements for JI projects.

The Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) is the most developed of the three mechanisms under the Kyoto Protocol. Article 12 establishes the foundation of the Clean Development Mechanism. It states: "A clean development mechanism is hereby defined." Its main objectives include assisting parties not included in Annex I, namely developing countries, in achieving sustainable development. Paragraph 2 of the same article provides: "The purpose of the clean development mechanism shall be to assist Parties not included in Annex I [...] in achieving compliance with their quantified emission limitation and reduction commitments under Article 3".

The CDM is therefore open to countries not listed in Annex I. Paragraph 3(a) states: "Parties not included in Annex I will benefit from project activities resulting in certified emission reductions...". It enables developed countries to meet their targets by purchasing emission reductions from countries that have achieved reductions in excess of their targets, and it assists developing countries in achieving sustainable development. Thus, two main objectives are emphasised: to assist developing countries in achieving sustainable development and to enable developed countries to meet their quantitative emission reduction targets under the Kyoto Protocol. Likewise, the provisions of the Cancun Agreement provide safeguards and instruments for the REDD+ initiatives, requiring States to address and respect the rights of local and indigenous peoples throughout the life cycle of REDD+ projects. Particularly, it requires states' actions, inter alia, to be consistent, transparent, and effective, addressing the risk or reversal. Of greater relevance is the requirement to respect the knowledge and rights of indigenous peoples and local community members. This includes their full and effective participation, taking into account relevant international obligations, including those enshrined in the United Nations General Assembly's Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, as well as national circumstances and laws. The normative character of the requirements to respect the rights of local and indigenous

communities to the benefits of REDD+ is reinforced through various decisions of the COP. Decision 2 of COP 17 and COP 16 have also reinvigorated states' obligations not only to ensure and respect international requirements on the rights of local indigenous communities but also the requirement to enact appropriate national laws. The requirements to adopt national laws should be understood in light of Principle 10 of the Rio Declaration. It imposed a positive obligation upon states to enact legislative frameworks and ensure the interplay of administrative measures to provide redress and remedy, compensating for losses incurred by local and indigenous communities (The Rio Declaration on Environment & Development, 1992).

Between 2005 and 2011, the carbon market mechanisms saw substantial expansion. This period also marked the second time the EU Emission Trading Scheme (EU ETS) was linked to the Kyoto mechanisms, leading to increased demand for private sector carbon credits (Shishlov, Morel, & Bellassen, 2016). During this "gold rush" period, criticism arose about the uneven geographical distribution of projects and environmental integrity issues related to baselines and additionality. Between 2012 and 2014, carbon markets experienced a drop in prices. This was due to the EU ETS reaching its quantitative limits on offsets and the absence of a new international regime, resulting in a decline in demand for governments. It was only between 2015 and 2018, during the gradual stabilisation of the international climate regime, that a significant milestone in combating climate change was achieved. The Paris Agreement established ambitious global mitigation targets, aiming to keep the global temperature rise well below 2°C and limit the increase to 1.5°C. Moreover, it aims to achieve a balance between emissions from sources and removals by sinks by the second half of the century. The Paris Agreement shifted REDD+ from Kyoto's compliance mechanisms to cooperative approaches under Article 6, enabling results-based payments via Emission Reductions (ER) programs. Of more relevance, Article 6 allows parties to pursue voluntary cooperation that can involve the use of 'internationally transferred mitigation outcomes' (ITMOs) to achieve their nationally determined contributions (NDCs). Similarly, Article 6.4 introduces a new crediting mechanism within the international framework oversight. Not only does the Agreement establish a voluntary mechanism for crediting, but its REDD+ mechanisms are also relatively general, which could be seen as a form of 'constructive ambiguity' to achieve consensus on credits and rights. Likewise, as it may appear, the Paris Agreement REDD+ has only increased complexity through global participation in mitigation. There are key lessons to be drawn from Article 6.4 mechanism. These include the need to ensure environmental integrity, regulatory confirmation at the national level, the compulsory quantification of emission reductions under international oversight, and the need to address double counting to avoid overlap with carbon crediting programmes and domestic schemes (Schneider et al., 2024). Likewise, and unlike the CDM's transparency provisions, mechanisms established under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement must ensure public access to project documentation and decision-making processes, as well as implementation of performance monitoring for auditors to enhance accountability and integrity in the validation process. Article 5 enjoins state parties: to implement and support, including through results-based payments, Policy approaches

and positive incentives for activities relating to reducing emissions from deforestation and forest degradation,; and alternative policy approaches, such as joint mitigation and adaptation approaches for the integral and sustainable management of forests, while reaffirming the importance of incentivising, as appropriate, non-carbon benefits associated with such approaches. While this article imposes some obligation upon states, there is a need to ensure the suitability of mitigation activities. The focus must be on high-hanging projects to ensure ambitious NDCs and avoid cheap mitigation projects. Ensuring a high likelihood of additionality to specific mitigation actions. Although the Paris Agreement established global goals aimed at achieving additional emission reductions, contributing to sustainable development, and raising climate ambition over time, its adoption has only heightened complexity due to increased global participation in mitigation efforts. Unlike the Kyoto Protocol, which only covers developed countries, the Paris Agreement established a new framework for voluntary cooperation that requires global participation (de Lassus St-Genies, 2024). The transition from the Kyoto mechanisms to Article 6.4 has increased the complexity and cost of the system. The Paris Agreement requires Parties to submit their nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), which indicate mitigation targets set on a voluntary basis by each Party. This new regime, however, resulted in a significant level of heterogeneity complicating mitigation accounting (Kreibich & Obergassel, 2016). The international climate regime has thus evolved from an approach based on mandatory emissions commitments to a system of voluntary government pledges. Thus, the transition toward a voluntary regime can be viewed as a fragmented global carbon market landscape characterised by diverse approaches that will affect the development of carbon markets in the future (Redmond & Convery, 2015). Likewise, the provisions for market mechanisms, as outlined in Articles 6.2 and 6.4, lack their modalities and procedures, and the practical implementation remains uncertain (Michaelowa, Shishlov, & Brescia, 2019). While the international carbon market remains uncertain, an increasing number of domestic carbon pricing initiatives have been launched worldwide over the past several years.

Mapping the Congo's Potential in Carbon Emissions and the REED+ Benefits

The Republic of Congo falls in one of the regions identified as deforestation fronts around the world, as presented in Figure 1. These fronts, potential carbon resources/stocks, are feared they be at imminent risk; inevitable deforestation and forest degradation will persist unless locally relevant, collective, and integrated approaches are adopted (Pacheco et al., 2021). Furthermore, the Congo Basin is under threat due to the exploitation of its rich mineral resources and associated infrastructure developments (World Bank, 2016). The intact forest landscape, commonly defined as an unbroken forest expanse without any signs of human activities, has been significantly reduced, as indicated by the overlay between 2000 and 2020, as presented in Figure I. It is estimated that by 2000, forest carbon stock loss had reached 12,000 ha and increased to 13,800 ha by 2020 without benefiting the local and indigenous communities (Ritchie & Roser, 2021).

Figure 1

Intact Forest Landscape Deforestation in the Republic of Congo (ROC) between 2000 and 2020

The debilitating effects of forest loss, a livelihood source for indigenous communities in the republic, are proven and irrefutable. Forest deforestation is also considered one of the leading factors in exacerbating global warming and climate change, as it contributes to the release of carbon emissions from forests (United Nations (UN), 2005). What is encouraging is that there is still hope for the implementation of REDD+ mechanisms. In comparison to other fronts, the magnitude and pace of deforestation of the 23.9 million ha of forest is considered low in the Republic of Congo. Therefore, to safeguard these forest resources for the benefit of society, several approaches must be implemented, and one of interest in this chapter is the securing of carbon rights for indigenous people and communities.

The overview of key decisions for REDD+ highlights that the needs of local and indigenous communities, as well as the bundle of carbon rights, must be recognised and addressed by developing country Parties. However, it falls short of providing means on how this must be operationalised at the local level. It is unclear who holds the rights and whether there are fair and equitable benefits from carbon financing, transactions, and markets (Skutsch, Mand, & Turnhout, 2018). The question remains: to what extent do the country's legal frameworks ensure the fair and equitable redistribution of the carbon rights to local and indigenous communities, taking into account their expectations, including how to compensate for their lost rights? It is therefore essential to analyse the legal basis of carbon rights at both the international and national levels to determine a country's willingness and readiness to compensate or redistribute benefits to local and indigenous communities.

National Implementation of Carbon Rights in the Republic of Congo

As indicated in the map, the Republic of the Congo, along with the six (6) other African countries, is covered by the Congo Basin Forest as the second largest tropical forest in the world after the Amazon. The Congolese Forest estate is estimated to be an area of more than 20 million hectares, or more than 60 % of the national territory, and the forest revenue, particularly the timber, represents nearly 5 % of GDP through the exportation of varied species of timber (sapelli, sipo, okoume, limba, wenge, padouk, iroko...). The Congo forest

industry is, however, dominated by private foreign companies. To secure the forest, the country joined the Forest Law Enforcement, Governance, and Trade initiative to control wood poaching and related trade.

Furthermore, the country has signed a national programme on Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation in Developing Countries "REDD+). These initiatives have largely contributed to and shaped the national forest law or code.

Article 1 of the forest code states the purpose of the national forest law to establish fundamental principles for the organisation and management of the national forest, as well as to define the rules on the exploitation and trade applicable to forest products. The forest code distinguishes between two categories of forests: national or state domains and private forests or domains. The state domain encompasses forests within the private domain of the State, as well as forests of legal persons governed by public law and community forests. Article 15 is more relevant to the community forests and recognises four types of community forests. The natural forest located in the series of community development of a forest concession to be developed, the forest plantation located on the land of a local community or indigenous populations, the forest whose initiative for the creation and sustainable management comes from a local community and the natural forest located on the territory of a community, local and indigenous peoples, which has been classified for their benefit. According to Article 40, this classification is subject to the principle of free, informed and prior consent of the populations concerned after consulting with civil society organisations in the constituency concerned. It is praiseworthy that the forest code makes provision for the community forests, in that it recognises the rights of local and indigenous communities to possess forests. Not only do local and indigenous people have the right to possess forests, but also, and more importantly, the state continues to ensure the conservation and sustainable use of forests by local and indigenous people through the municipal council. The legal recognition of the rights of local and indigenous communities over the forest implies that any benefits arising from exploitation belong to these communities. Article 19 of the Forest Code underscores these rights: "Income from the sale of forest products of any kind resulting from the exploitation of community forests accrues to the local communities and or to the indigenous populations concerned."

It should be emphasised that local communities also have the right to use the protected forest. These rights include the rights to farming, the use of water, and any other resources necessary for the satisfaction of their personal needs for survival and subsistence. Relevant to this discussion is the issue of access to generic resources and the sharing of benefits derived from their exploitation. As far as carbon credits are concerned, the determination of the redistribution of REDD+ benefits largely depends on the rights one may possess over the forest. Whether legal or customary, the people holding tenure rights are entitled to the benefits arising from the Carbon Fund. In this context, carbon credits may have a different legal status, depending on the national legislation. They may be considered as movable property or a natural fruit of the tree.

In the former case, the owner may freely transfer the rights without public order restrictions and have an individual right to a heritage asset having a pecuniary value. Additionally, as we will see, credits on the carbon can also be assimilated into securities related to a natural resource (the carbon sequestered/avoided). The sequestered carbon is therefore considered to be either the natural

result of a biological process of storage in the biomass or a natural fruit of a tree. As a natural resource, carbon credits may be protected by specific laws and also be appropriated by the public as part of the public domain. Whether a natural fruit from the tree, planted or not. Traditionally, fruits are perceived by the owner of the property as one of the elements of the right of ownership (fructus). This qualification is very important in situations where the owner of the land is not necessarily the owner of the trees, and vice versa. In the Republic of Congo, the rights to carbon credits are governed by the law and are attributed based on the rights of tenure. If the forest belongs to local communities, they retain the rights to carbon credits, whether because they own the forests or simply because they have the rights to use them. Article 180 of the forest code states:

"If the forests belong to the State, to local communities and to other legal persons under public law, the carbon credit belongs respectively to the State, to the local community or to another person under public law concerned. When carbon credits are managed by a project to reduce emissions linked to deforestation and forest degradation, including the sustainable management of forests, conservation of biodiversity, and an increase in forest carbon stocks, directly by a natural or legal person under private law, the latter is also considered a co-owner. However, holders of customary rights and rights of use are beneficiaries of carbon credits."

The forest code is very explicit about the rights of local and indigenous communities to benefit from carbon credits based on the legal status of the forest tenure. The law recognises the rights of local and indigenous communities to carbon credits generated, whether solely or jointly with a third party, as long as the project is implemented in forest land belonging to the local or indigenous community or simply because they have rights of usage. It should be emphasised that the national law of the Republic of Congo requires that any benefits arising from the use of forest genetic resources, from the subsequent commercialisation, must be shared in a fair and equitable manner between the parties providing such resources and parties acquiring them, on mutually agreed terms. Applying a "bundle of rights" theory provides a crucial framework for understanding the divergence between national legislation and specific contractual agreements regarding carbon ownership and benefit-sharing. The concept of a bundle of rights enables us to disaggregate property ownership into distinct entitlements, including the right to use, manage, exclude, and transfer resources (Birben et al., 2025). In the context of carbon finance, this determines who holds the right to manage forest carbon and who is entitled to pecuniary benefits. The 2020 Forest Code recognises four types of community forests based on legal or customary tenure.

Carbon ownership (Fructus) is therefore explicitly tied to carbon credit ownership. Credits belong to the legal person holding public or private tenure. Crucially, holders of customary rights and rights of use are also beneficiaries of carbon credits, even if they are not the legal owners of the land. Unlike the Forest Code, the Sangha-Likouala Agreement (FCPF/WB) defined land tenure jurisdictionally within specific departments. It creates assigned amount units (AAUs) and authorises credit creation via the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM). It also provides a detailed cost-benefit sharing model that stakeholders must agree to for payments to be unlocked. Sets aside a Dedicated Grant Mechanism for Indigenous Peoples to offset costs and enhance sustainability. The 2020 Forest Code attempts to integrate customary bundle rights at a high level into national law by codifying IPLC beneficiaries based

on rights of usage (Article 180). In contrast, the Sangha-Likouala agreement acts as a functional operationalisation of this bundle within a specific jurisdictional context. Likewise, the Code provides the legal right to fructus (carbon fruits), and the Agreement defines the fiscal mechanism for benefit sharing. The Agreement's approach is more ethical and sustainability-driven, treating benefit-sharing as a tool to offset costs and improve effective implementation. However, it must be flexible and provide dispute resolution to be genuinely equitable.

Although the Republic of Congo has developed national legal frameworks on REDD+, they remain complex and underdeveloped. The REDD+ initiative, particularly its policies on benefit sharing, is influenced by both natural resources management policies and specific REDD+ Policies. The country's legal framework also includes multiple funds claiming shares of carbon revenues, leading to a lack of coordination. Recent laws emphasise the need for participatory decision-making and the inclusion of local communities in benefits sharing. More alarming is the incompleteness of the institutional and legal framework. The country framework is outdated, whereas ministerial regulations meant to complement the REDD+ policies are pending finalisation. Law No. 22/030 of 2022 on the rights of indigenous pygmy peoples awaits the implementing decree. There are also concerns raised by most stakeholders regarding administrative charges and competing interests between the government and indigenous peoples, which hinder the effectiveness of policy. The exclusion of local communities and the lack of capacity to access REDD+ benefits may lead to social conflict, which could undermine the primary objective of REDD+ projects. This is because the REDD+ benefit-sharing narrative is often overshadowed by discussions on the carbon market.

The Conundrum of the Legal Status of Carbon Credits and Participatory Justice (Rawlsian Approach)

The findings reveal that while the Republic of Congo's legislation provides robust provisions for access and extraction rights, aspects related to management, exclusion, and alienation exhibit certain limitations. Notably, many stakeholders have highlighted the constrained right of alienation in public forests, impacting on the effective utilisation of forest carbon rights (Kengoum, Thuy, & Mihigo, 2024). The REDD+ aims to incentivise actors for maintaining or restoring forests, thereby reducing carbon emissions. Carbon credits represent the reductions in greenhouse gas emissions that are sold to offset the buyer's own greenhouse gas emissions (Aldy & Halem, 2024).

Carbon rights are therefore understood as title to carbon credits and have an odd status in the REDD+ debate (Streck, 2020). Some countries viewed credits as property rights, while others as a "bundle of rights". Particularly, in the USA, the legal differences across states have created future challenges for the cap-and-trade market (Monterubio, 2011). These include the likelihood of disputes over carbon ownership in the event that the market expands and potentially links with other markets. Likewise, private traders may struggle to clearly define property rights in sale contracts and specify the relevant jurisdiction in the event of disputes. Thus, there is a need for REDD+ mechanisms to unify the legal status of carbon credits, rather than leaving this responsibility to individual states. Although the Republic of Congo recognise carbon credits as a bundle of rights, the challenge remains when expanding its market to countries which

do not. To promote efficiency in the REDD+ mechanism, buyers and sellers must be assured of their rights over the carbon they trade. While state efforts in this regard are laudable, the disparate cap-and-trade programs have yielded inconsistent benefits, including the sharing of carbon credits. Since this is accepted by most, carbon credit generates (economic) 'rents', i.e., revenues exceeding the full cost of the corresponding effort. Carbon rights are primarily based on entitlements derived from land tenure of forest resources. Indigenous peoples and traditional communities are central to carbon credits, with their identities deeply tied to ancestral rights and their natural environments. This raises concerns about the power dynamics between indigenous interests and dominant actors, such as private traders and the government, in decision-making processes. Indigenous self-determination is closely tied to their unique lifestyles and extensive territories, with rights rooted in ancestral claims rather than state grants. Indigenous peoples, particularly Pygmy populations, inhabit a vast territory that extends from west to east along the central African belt, from the Congo Basin to Lake Victoria. However, their numbers and actual distribution are not known precisely. It is estimated that there are approximately 920,000 Pygmies (over 60%) residing in favourable forest areas in Central Africa (Olivero et al., 2016). This only highlights the need for protection and justice. The UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples acknowledges their historical vulnerabilities and ongoing threats from economic expansion.

The access and benefit-sharing regime of carbon credits can be better dealt with in the context of John Rawls's theory of Justice as Fairness. This theory makes a significant contribution, one that has yet to be explored, to shedding light on the conflicts between commutative and distributive justice in the context of carbon credits (Kleba, 2013). Generally, any work on access and benefit-sharing raises issues of justice grounded in intuition (Kleba, 2009). Likewise, States often oppress individuals more than cultural groups, monopolising legitimate force, and Indigenous claims frequently conflict with state interests, particularly regarding land rights and resource exploitation. However, the legitimacy of legal interventions to protect indigenous individual rights depends on their involvement and support for their development. Justice as Fairness can illuminate conflicts of commutative and distributive justice within the access and benefit-sharing framework. Rawls's Theory of Justice proposes a social contract negotiated under a veil of ignorance, ensuring fairness for all citizens (Rawls, 2003). It consists of two principles: equal basic liberties and social or economic inequalities benefiting the least advantaged. This framework emphasises the need for equal opportunities in education and health, aiming to balance pluralism and democracy. Indigenous peoples and traditional communities are central to the REDD+ mechanisms, with their rights recognised under Article 8(j). Despite recognising their rights, indigenous groups faced challenges in asserting their rights against powerful interests. The Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples provides a legal framework acknowledging their vulnerabilities. These include genocide, forced acculturation, and displacement, leading to significant cultural and territorial threats. In countries where these rights are recognised, more needs to be done, including harmonising customary law with positive law. Since indigenous claims often conflict with state interests, particularly regarding land rights and the exploitation of resources, the legitimacy of legal interventions depends on local involvement and respect for indigenous traditions. Particularly, in

the context of carbon credits, there is a need to reposition Rawls' difference principle. The concept of the least advantaged should shift from wealth-based definitions to those focused on realising citizenship. In this regard, Rawlsian principles emphasise the importance of non-material goods, such as education and political participation, in achieving citizenship. Cultural diversity requires recognising different lifestyles and the material conditions necessary for their realisation. Indigenous communities face economic and cultural vulnerabilities, necessitating policies that support their rights. Access and benefit sharing also raises the issue of land titles between private landowners, indigenous communities, and governmental bodies, complicating negotiations for many indigenous groups. Many countries have adopted a dual reward system to strike a balance between fairness and efficiency, allocating benefits to both landowners and broader conservation efforts. Access and benefit sharing of carbon credits requires fairness and equity (Kankeu et al., 2020). Considering that legal disparities also exist between ILCs and large companies, this creates unequal negotiation power, leading to suboptimal contracts. Such disparities exist among indigenous leaders who are demanding higher profit shares, reflecting their dissatisfaction and shortfall in ensuring equitable access to benefits for all stakeholders with current agreements (Kreibich et al., 2017). The application of the principle of fairness and equity has a more social dimension. John Rawls suggests that there are two key aspects of the social dimension of justice: fair equality of opportunity and a social system that acts for the greatest benefit of the least advantaged in society (Rawls, 2017). This implies that any actions by the government should prioritise and promote the well-being of local and indigenous communities. Unlike many other fronts presented on the map, the country's capacity to produce timber does not affect its ability to earn carbon credit. While respecting the tenure and the rights of entitlement of holders, including indigenous peoples, the study highlights the importance of clear definitions and regulations regarding carbon rights, particularly in a country with dominant public forest ownership, to promote sustainable carbon management and equitable participation in international carbon trading mechanisms.

Furthermore, this also means that there is a possibility of establishing sharing presumptions regarding the sharing and distribution of property rights to carbon credits in the Republic of Congo. In particular, the nations' series of negotiations and participation culminated in a landmark Sangha-Likouala REDD+ agreement, signed in 2021, to unlock US\$41.8 million between the Republic of Congo and the World Bank's Forest Carbon Partnership Facility (FCPF) (World Bank, 2021). The concept stage and project information documents clearly state that a budget from this REDD+ initiative will be set aside as a Dedicated Grant mechanism for Indigenous Peoples, along with a detailed cost-benefit sharing model involving local communities and other stakeholders (World Bank, 2020). It is essential that benefit-sharing agreements be flexible, allowing for necessary adjustments based on learning, and provide clear mechanisms for dispute resolution. Likewise, benefit-sharing is an ethical obligation that helps offset the costs and make REDD+ more effective, equitable and sustainable. It is always suggested that the principles and criteria of governance assume all their importance in the benefits sharing of the REDD+. From the perspective of implementing a national system of sharing of revenues or advantages, a set of measures is recommended. A proposal for distributing the benefits resulting from the REDD+

process should be made in accordance with the nature of the advantages.

Conclusion

The Republic of Congo is categorised as a tropical forest biome, and it's under threat as it falls within one of the world's deforestation fronts. However, the rate of deforestation in this region is still considered low, which provides hope for the implementation of REDD+ mechanisms and benefits local and indigenous communities through carbon rights. Following the World Bank Carbon Fund, adopted shortly after the Warsaw Framework for REDD+ (December 2013), many countries, such as Ecuador, Costa Rica, and Mexico, have found ways to ensure the participation of all stakeholders, including local and indigenous communities, while considering their expectations. This justifies the diversity of approaches to benefit sharing within the countries involved. The issue of benefit sharing is closely linked to that of participation and the rights of local and indigenous populations, as well as forest users. While the Republic of Congo has made progress in developing REDD+ benefit-sharing mechanisms, significant challenges remain. These include improving transparency, clarifying institutional responsibilities, addressing elite capture, ensuring timely payments, and enhancing the inclusion of local communities and women. Future efforts should focus on learning from existing projects, strengthening safeguards, and creating a functional national REDD+ registry to ensure effective, efficient, and equitable benefit sharing.

Fairness is a major and highly controversial issue in the debate over benefit sharing. This article proposes the Rawlsian approach of Justice as Fairness as a sustainable way of balancing conflicts over distributive and collective justice. The Rawlsian principle of difference makes a significant contribution here, particularly in light of the post-Kyoto REDD+ mechanisms, which have been further complicated by challenges related to voluntary global governance, significance level of heterogeneity and a fragmented global carbon market landscape characterised by diverse approaches that will affect the development of carbon markets in the future.

References

- Aldy, J.E., & Halem, Z.M. (2024). The evolving role of greenhouse gas emission offsets in combating climate change. *Review of Environmental Economics and Policy*, 18(2), 212-233.
- Alemagi, D., Minang, P.A., Feudjio, M., & Duguma, L. (2014). REDD+ readiness process in Cameroon: An analysis of multi-stakeholder perspectives. *Climate Policy (Earthscan)*, 14(6), 709-733.
- Birben, O., Elvan, O.D., Aydm, A., Perkumiene, D., Skema, M., & Aleinikovas, M. (2025). Property rights for forest carbon: A conceptual perspective. *Sustainability*, 17(2), 442.
- Congo Industrie (AC), Malaysian companies; Sicofor, a Chinese company; Foralac and Trabec, European companies or Mokabi, a French subsidiary of Rougier Group, etc.
- Congolaise Industrielle des Bois (CIB), a Congolese subsidiary of Singaporean Olam Group, which operates nearly 1.3 million hectares of forest in the northern part of the country; Industrie Forestiere de Ouessou (JFO), a subsidiary of German-Swiss Danzer Group; Likouala Timber, an Italian corporation; Taman Industries and Asia.
- Cotula, L., & Mayers, J. (2009). Tenure in REDD start-point or afterthought? *IIED*, 9.
- de Lassus St-Genies, G. (2024). The market mechanisms of the Paris Agreement and the Kyoto Protocol: A legal comparison. In G. de Lassus St-Genies (Ed.), *Research handbook on the law of the Paris agreement* (pp. 240-261). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Decision 2 of COP 17 "Outcome of the work of the Ad Hoc Working Group on Long-term Cooperative Action under the Convention" Conference of the Parties (COP) 1 November 2011. Available at <https://unfccc.int/decisions/?f%5B0%5D=body%3A1343&f%5B1%5D=conference%3A3461>;
- Draft decision -/CP.16 Outcome of the work of the Ad Hoc Working Group on long-term Cooperative Action under the Convention.
- Elliot Report on Estimate of 2005-2012 emissions for stationary installations to reflect the current scope (2013-2020) of the EU ETS. Eionet Report - ETC/CME 2019/1 April 2019.
- Forest Law Enforcement, Governance and Trade. The EU's FLEGT Action Plan was established in 2003 <https://flegtvpfacility.org/flegt/#:~:text=FLEGT,FLEGT%20st%20and%20for%20Forest%20Law%20Enforcement%2C%20Governance%20and%20Trade,trade%20in%20legally%20produced%20timber>
- <https://www.un.org/development/desa/indigenouspeoples/declaration-on-the-rights-of-indigenous-peoples.html>
- Kankeu, R.S., Demaze, M.T., Krott, M., Sonwa, D.J., & Ongolo, S. (2020). Governing knowledge transfer for deforestation monitoring: Insights from REDD+ projects in the Congo Basin region. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 111, 102081.
- Kengoum, F., Phan, T.T., Tirumenyerwa Mihigo, B.P. (2024). *REDD+ benefit sharing mechanisms in the Democratic Republic of the Congo: Legal and institutional frameworks, policy implementation, and project experiences*. Working Paper 27. Bogor, Indonesia: CIFOR and Nairobi, Kenya: TCRAF.
- Kengoum, F., Thuy, P.T., & Mihigo, B.P. (2024). *REDD+ benefit-sharing mechanisms in the Democratic Republic of Congo*.
- Kleba, J.B. (2009). A socio-legal inquiry into the protection of disseminated traditional knowledge: Learning from Brazilian Cases. In E.C. Kamau and G. Winter (Eds.), *Genetic resources, traditional knowledge and the law* (pp. 1-19). London: Earthscan.
- Kleba, J.B. (2013). Fair biodiversity politics with and beyond Rawls. *Law, Environment and Development Journal*, 9, 221.
- Kreibich, N., & Obergassel, W. (2016). *Carbon markets after Paris: how to account for the transfer of 39 mitigation results?* Wuppertal: Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment and Energy.
- Kreibich, N., Hermwille, L., Warnecke, C., & Arens, C. (2017). An update on the clean development 36 mechanism in Africa in times of market crisis. *Climate and Development*, 9(2), 178-190.
- Kyoto Protocol to the Convention on Climate Change, Climate Change Secretariat and the United Nations Environmental Programme Information Unit. UNEP/IUC/99/10. Article 3 Law o. 1 o. 33-2020 of July 8, 2020, on the Forest Code.
- Michaelowa, A., Shishlov, I., & Brescia, D. (2019). Evolution of international carbon markets: Lessons for the Paris agreement. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 10(6), e613.
- Monterubio, J. (2011). Recognition of property rights in carbon credits under California's new greenhouse gas cap-and-trade program. *Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy*, 12, 32.
- Nomani, M.Z.M. (2020). The access and benefit-sharing regime: An Environmental justice perspective. *Environmental Policy and Law*, 49(4-5), 259-263.
- Olivero, J., Fa, J.E., Farfan, M.A., Lewis, J., Hewlett, B., Breuer, T., Carpaneto, G.M., Fernandez, M., Germe, F., Hattori, S., & Head, J. (2016). Distribution and numbers of Pygmies in Central African forests. *PLoS One*, 11(1), e0144499.
- Pacheco, P., Mo, K., Dudley, J., Shapiro, A., Aguilar-Amuchástegui, Ling, P.Y., Anderson, C., & Marx, A. (2021). *Deforestation fronts: Drivers and responses in a changing world*. WWF, Gland, Switzerland.
- Rawls, J. (2003). *Justice as fairness: A restatement 136-139*. 176 (Cambridge (Mass): The Belknap Press, 3rd print 2003) [hereafter Rawls (2003)].
- Rawls, J. (2017). A theory of justice. In J. Rawls (Ed.), *Applied ethics* (pp. 21-29). Routledge.
- Redmond, L., & Convery, F. (2015). The global carbon market-mechanism landscape: pre and post 8 2020 perspectives. *Climate Policy*, 15(5), 647-669.
- Rio Declaration on Environment and Development (1992) Principle 10. Rio de Janeiro from 3 to 14 June 1992.
- Ritchie, H., & Roser, M. (2021). *Forests and deforestation*. Published online at OurWorldInData.org. Retrieved from: <https://ourworldindata.org/forests-and-deforestation> [Online Resource]
- Schneider, L., Jung, H., Haase, I., Michaelowa, A., Kessler, J., Oberpriller, Q., & Füssler, J. (2024). Lessons Learned from the Kyoto Mechanisms for the Article 6.4 Mechanism. *Climate Change*, 2.
- Shishlov, I., Morel, R., & Bellassen, V. (2016). Compliance of the parties to the Kyoto protocol in the 1st commitment period. *Climate Policy*, 16(6), 768-782.
- Skutsch, M., & Turnhout, E. (2018). How REDD+ is performing in communities. *Forests*, 9, 638.
- Streck, C. (2020). Who owns REDD+? Carbon markets, carbon rights and entitlements to REDD+ finance. *Forests*, 11(9), 959.
- UNFCCC (2010). *Decision 1/CP.16*. The Cancun Agreements: Outcome of the work of the Ad Hoc Working Group on Long-term Cooperative Action under the Convention. FCCC/CP/2010/7/Add.1 (paragraph 72)
- UNFCCC (2007). *Decision 2/CP.13*. Reducing emissions from deforestation in developing countries: approaches to stimulate action. FCCC/CP/2007/6/Add.1 (page 8).

- United Nations (UN) (2005). *United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change: Item 6 of the provisional agenda, Reducing emissions from deforestation in developing countries: Approaches to stimulate action*. FCCC/CP/2005/MISC.1
- United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP) was adopted by the General Assembly on Thursday, 13 September 2007. Available at United Nations Framework Convention for Climate Change UNFCCC/CP/2001/13/Add.2 Decision 16/CP.7 Article 6 Annex D, Paragraphs 21, 23 and 24.
- World Bank (2016). *Balancing mining development and forest conservation in the Congo basin (English)*. Washington, D.C. : World Bank Group. <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/266991471346447238/pdf/ACS18913-REVISED-PUBLIC-Output-P146347-BalancingMiningForests-CongoBasin-Aug2016Final.pdf>
- World Bank (2021). *World Bank and Republic of Congo Sign Agreement to Reduce Carbon Emissions and Preserve Forests*. Press Release NO: 2021/126/AFR. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2021/05/03/world-bank-and-republic-of-congo-sign-agreement-to-reduce-carbon-emissions-and-preserve-forests>
- World Bank (2017). *Project information document / integrated safeguards data sheet (PID/ISDS) Concept Stage*. Report No.: PIDISDSC22031. <https://ewdata.rightsindevelopment.org/files/documents/61/WB-P163361.pdf>
- World Bank (2020). *Republic of Congo Ministry of Forest Economy: Benefit Sharing Plan For The Emission Reduction Program (ER-P) for Sangha Likouala*. <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/962821607411556246/pdf/Republic-of-Congo-Benefit-Sharing-Plan-for-the-Emission-Reduction-Program-ERP-for-Sangha-Likouala.pdf>.

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